

Recovery of platinum using chlorination of DOER residue

S. Vijayalakshmi*, S. Annapoorani, V. Hemalatha and K. Sankaran

Analytical Chemistry and Spectroscopy Section, Materials Chemistry Division, Chemistry Group,
Indira Gandhi Centre for Atomic Research, Kalpakkam-603 102, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : sviji@igcar.gov.in

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An analytical procedure using chlorination of the platinum residue of Direct Oxide Electrochemical Reduction (DOER) experiments was standardized for the recovery of platinum. Pt anode in the DOER process was found to get attacked during the process resulting in residue containing Pt. Some of the residue samples are soluble in aqua regia, but not all of them. Therefore chlorination procedure was standardized for the dissolution of platinum residue. The procedure for converting platinum from solution to platinum sulphide precipitate and then to pure platinum by heating was also standardized.

Sample was taken in an alumina crucible and was kept inside a quartz vessel with appropriate quartz tubes for chlorination. Chlorination was carried out by passing chlorine gas through quartz vessel kept at a suitable temperature. Chlorination was standardized by optimizing the concentration of admixture (sodium chloride), temperature and time of chlorination. Sample to sodium chloride ratio of 1 : 25, temperature of 600 K and 3 h duration for chlorination were found to be the optimum experimental conditions. After the chlorination, the resi-

due was found to dissolve completely on heating with aqua regia. Completion of dissolution was ensured by analyzing the dissolved solution using ICP-OES.

After the dissolution of residue, pH was adjusted to 1 and platinum was separated as platinum sulphide by the addition of sodium sulphide solution. Recovery of platinum as platinum sulphide was measured by ICP-OES and it was found to be around 95%. Pure platinum was recovered by heating the platinum sulphide. The recovery of platinum by heating step was also confirmed by analysis using ICP-OES.

The above chlorination procedure offered complete dissolution of residue and thus offers complete recovery of Pt from the residue of DOER process.

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